

Studies in Ion-exchange Equilibria. Part IV. Exchange of Univalent Cations of Amberlite IR-112, Amberlite IRC-50, and Sulphonated Coal in Aqueous Ethanol

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Cation-exchange studies have been performed for univalent ions in aqueous ethanolic solutions with a porous sulphonic acid type of exchanger (Amberlite IR-112), a weakly acidic carboxylic type of exchanger (Amberlite IRC-50), and a carbonaceous exchanger (sulphonated coal) in hydrogen forms. Observations have been made regarding linear increase of percentage of exchange and regular increase of $\log_{10} K_2$ with increase of ethanol percentage. Effect of the quantity of resin and of presence of anions on exchange of cations have also been studied.

In an earlier communication¹, cationic exchange-equilibrium studies in aqueous ethanol were reported on Amberlite IR-120, a nuclear sulphonic acid type, highly cross-linked resin. In the present communication, the work has been extended to other types of resins, viz., Amberlite IR-112, a porous comparatively less-investigated resin, Amberlite IRC 50, a weakly acidic carboxylic type of resin, and sulphonated coal, a carbonaceous exchanger. Studies have been performed with lithium, sodium, potassium, silver, and thallos ions in aqueous ethanol solutions to ascertain variabilities of percentage of exchange, affinity sequences, and apparent equilibrium constants with ethanol concentrations. The effect of the quantity of resin and of presence of an anion on the exchange of a cation have also been studied.

EXPERIMENTAL

The stock solutions of the ions (0.1 *N*) and the ethanolic solution (0.0 to 60%) containing cation concentrations of 0.05 *N*, 0.025 *N*, and 0.01 *N* were prepared as in previous studies¹. Amberlite IR-112 (H) and IRC-50 (H) of Rohm and Haas Co., Philadelphia were of A. R. quality; sulphonated coal (H) was prepared from semi-bituminous Indian coal².

The procedure followed for equilibrium batch studies was the same as described earlier.¹ Such equilibrium studies were carried out for all ions under study at three concentrations (0.05 *N*, 0.025 *N*, and 0.0125 *N*) on Amberlite IR-112 and sulphonated coal; only alkali metal ions were studied at 0.1 *N*, 0.025 *N*, and 0.01 *N* concentrations on Amberlite IRC-50. The percentage of ethanol in aqueous solutions were varied from 0 to 60 in all cases.

Effect of the quantity of the resin on exchange of potassium ion (0.025 *N*) was studied on Amberlite IR-112 only by varying its quantity as 0.5, 0.75, and 1.0, using different

1. *This Journal*, 1963, **40**, 124.

2. Bafna *et al.*, *Curr. Sci.*, 1951, **20**, 233; *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1952, **11B**, 134.

STUDIES IN ION-EXCHANGE EQUILIBRIA

ethanolic solutions. Similarly effect of anions on the exchange of potassium ion (0.0 was studied with 0.5 g. of this resin, using its chloride, bromide, iodide, and nitrate.

All calculations for apparent equilibrium constants were done according to mass action relationship used by Kressman and Kitchener³ and used by us in earlier investigations^{1,4} For the sake of brevity, results at only one concentration (0.025*N*) have been shown graphically.

DISCUSSION

The results of these equilibrium studies indicate a linear increase for percentage of ionic exchange with the percentage of ethanol (v/v) in cases of strongly acidic resin IR-112

and sulphonated coal (Fig. 1, A-B), but this increase is not linear for the weakly acidic resin IRC-50 (Fig. 1, C). Comparatively, for an ion in aqueous solutions, the percentage of exchange is more for a porous resin, less for the sulphonated coal, and least for the weakly acidic resin. The increase in the percentage of ethanol had a pronounced effect on the exchange of ions in the case of IRC-50 in which the exchange was sufficiently less in aqueous or 10-20% ethanol solutions, but increased to a very high value (even more than in other two resins) at 60% ethanol concentration.

The values for apparent equilibrium constant (K_a), depending on the extent of exchange, similarly increased with concentration of ethanol.

The above conclusions are similar to those which were arrived at previously¹ on Amberlite IR-120. The observed variations are therefore due to the combined effect of ion-dehydration caused

by presence of ethanol in aqueous solutions and the swelling effect on the resin in such solvents. The upward trend of the graphs shows that ion-dehydration

3. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 1190.

4. Bhatnagar, *this Journal*, 1962, 39, 79.

predominates and diminishes the size of the ions, thus causing their exchange more than in hydrated forms. The sequence in alkali metal ions therefore remains same, i.e., $\text{Li} < \text{Na} < \text{K}$. Thallium (I) exchanged more than all the other ions and maintained its sequence in ethanol solutions also. The position of silver ion changed with respect to the alkali metals (Na and K) as the ethanol concentration increased in the solution for reasons already suggested¹.

The effect of ionic concentration on K-H exchange of different ethanol concentrations was also studied. The percentage of exchange increased with ionic concentration, but K_a showed an increase up to a certain extent and then a decrease. Thus the conclusions of

FIG- 2. Amberlite IR-112.

Wiegner⁵ for aluminosilicate exchanger, of Kresman *et al*⁶ for phenol sulphonate, and of Bhatnagar *et al*⁷ for Amberlite IR-120 tally with the present ones for porous, weakly acidic, and carbonaceous exchangers. Similar conclusions were also arrived at by Bafna⁷, using acetone solutions for Amberlite IR-120.

An increase in resin quantity caused less exchange of potassium ion on Amberlite IR-112(H), confirming our previous results with IR-120 in the case of ethanol solutions and that of Bafna⁷ in the case of acetone solutions. But an increase in resin quantity increases the value of X_{AB} considerably and hence the values of K_a increase progressively

with resin quantity in grams.

Anions as chloride, bromide, iodide, and nitrate have also a pronounced effect on the exchange of cations (potassium in the present case). With an ion of bigger size, the cation exchange was less and *vice versa* (Fig. 2). Thus a decrease in ionic character of an otherwise electrovalent salt led to decreased exchange in partly nonaqueous systems.

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